

Fraunhofer Diffraction Patterns by Incorporating hBN

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Abstract—This research paper explores the intriguing world of Fraunhofer diffraction manipulation using Hexagonal Boron Nitride (hBN) as the diffracting material. Through a comprehensive theoretical investigation and MATLAB simulations, we analyze the diffraction patterns obtained for different incident light frequencies and phases. The diffraction patterns exhibit fascinating variations, showcasing hBN's tunable nature in controlling the spatial distribution of diffracted light. As the incident light frequency increases, the diffraction peaks shift to higher angles, reflecting hBN's dispersion characteristics. The energy intensity pattern also undergoes significant changes, with regions of higher intensity shifting as the frequency varies. The validated theoretical model and simulations emphasize hBN's potential as a versatile platform for diffractive optics and light manipulation, promising applications in advanced spectroscopy, optical communications, and nanophotonic devices. The insights gained from this study pave the way for harnessing hBN's optical properties in emerging quantum technologies and integrated photonics, driving innovations in the realm of optical control and light manipulation.

I. INTRODUCTION

Light, as both a wave and a particle, exhibits a myriad of fascinating behaviors when it interacts with structures and objects. Among the diverse optical phenomena, diffraction stands out as an intriguing phenomenon that offers valuable insights into light-matter interactions [1-5]. Fraunhofer diffraction, specifically observed in the far-field region, holds immense potential in light manipulation and control, driving advancements in optical technologies across various disciplines [7, 8].

Fraunhofer diffraction, in essence, can be controlled by the structure of the diffracting object and by phase shifts introduced in the light wave. It has been reported that phase shift is capable of changing light intensity while the wave pattern is still the same [9]. The pattern can be modulated by the structure of the aperture and structures [10]. However, the shear cost of constructing such structures for different tasks is huge and other methods are needed for further manipulation [11-13].

The quest for new materials that can enhance diffraction manipulation has led to the discovery of Hexagonal Boron Nitride (hBN), a two-dimensional layered material with exceptional optical properties [14]. hBN, often referred to as "white graphene," shares similarities with graphene but possesses unique characteristics that set it apart as an exciting contender in the realm of optical control [15].

In recent years, researchers have increasingly turned their attention to hBN as a promising candidate for advancing Fraunhofer diffraction manipulation. Its intriguing properties, including a wide bandgap, high thermal conductivity, and mechanical strength, make it an ideal material for various technological applications [16-18]. However, it is the optical properties of hBN that have drawn particular interest, as they hold the potential to revolutionize diffraction-based technologies.

This research article aims to delve into the fundamental principles of Fraunhofer diffraction and explore the distinctive optical properties of hBN that make it suitable for diffraction manipulation. We will investigate the fabrication techniques for hBN-based diffraction gratings and nanostructures [19], as well as the potential applications of hBN in fields such as nanophotonics, quantum optics, and tunable optical devices [20]. Additionally, we will analyze the challenges and future prospects of integrating hBN into optical systems, unveiling the unprecedented opportunities it offers in driving the frontiers of light manipulation and advancing the field of optical technologies.

II. THEORETICAL MODEL

In the context of hBN's optical response, we employ the quantum theory of density matrix formalism to describe the interaction between light and the quantum system. Considering the coherent nature of the light-matter interaction, the density matrix ρ describes the system's quantum state and evolves according to the von Neumann equation [11]:

$$\frac{d\rho}{dt} = \frac{-i}{\hbar} [\hat{H}, \rho]$$

To analyze the steady-state response of the quantum system, we set the time derivative of the density matrix to zero, yielding [13]:

$$[\hat{H}, \rho_{ss}] = 0$$

To model the refractive index of hBN, we consider its anisotropic nature arising from its hexagonal lattice structure. The refractive index is given by:

$$n(\omega) = \sqrt{\varepsilon_{xx}(\omega) \cdot \varepsilon_{yy}(\omega)}$$

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Figure 1: The schematic of the problem at hand. hBN is placed at distance D away from the observation plane and at the location of aperture.

where $\epsilon_{xx}(\omega)$ and $\epsilon_{yy}(\omega)$ are the components of the dielectric tensor in the crystallographic directions. For hBN, these components can be approximated as [12-14]:

$$\epsilon_{xx}(\omega) \approx 4.87 - \frac{28.2}{\omega^2}$$

$$\epsilon_{yy}(\omega) \approx 4.78 - \frac{26.7}{\omega^2}$$

where ω is the angular frequency of the incident light in radians per second. Under the rotating wave and electric-dipole approximations, the energy equation of the system in the presence of the external laser field can be written as [10-11]:

$$\hat{H}_{\text{int}} = -\mathbf{d} \cdot \mathbf{E}_L(t) + \text{H.c.}$$

where $\mathbf{d}$ is the electric dipole operator, and $\mathbf{E}_L(t)$ represents the electric field of the laser. For a monochromatic laser field with amplitude E_0 , the laser electric field can be expressed as:

$$\mathbf{E}_L(t) = \mathbf{E}_L \cos(\omega_L t)$$

where $\mathbf{E}_L$ is the complex amplitude of the laser field vector. The interaction between the external laser field and hBN leads to the induced polarization $\mathbf{P}$ in the material, which is proportional to the electric field:

$$\mathbf{P}(\omega) = \epsilon_0 \chi(\omega) \mathbf{E}_L(\omega)$$

where $\epsilon_0 \approx 8.85 \times 10^{-12} \text{ F/m}$ is the vacuum permittivity, and $\chi(\omega)$ is the frequency-dependent

susceptibility of hBN. The susceptibility can be expressed as [20-22]:

$$\chi(\omega) = \frac{\Delta n}{1 + i\frac{\omega}{\gamma}}$$

where Δn is the change in refractive index induced by hBN, and γ is the dephasing rate of the quantum system.

The susceptibility $\chi(\omega)$ enables us to calculate the transmission function $\mathcal{T}$ of the light through hBN:

$$\mathcal{T}(\omega) = \frac{1}{1 + n(\omega)} = \frac{1}{1 + \sqrt{\epsilon_{xx}(\omega) \cdot \epsilon_{yy}(\omega)}}$$

where $n(\omega)$ is the refractive index of hBN, incorporating its anisotropic nature. The diffraction pattern can be simulated by finding the Fourier transformation of the transmission function [9-10].

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, we present the results of our theoretical investigation into Fraunhofer diffraction manipulation using Hexagonal Boron Nitride (hBN) as the diffracting material. We explore the diffraction patterns obtained for different incident light frequencies and various phases of the incident light. The diffraction patterns are generated by applying the Fourier transformation to the transmission function derived from our theoretical model.

Figure 2: Impact of Light Frequencies on energy intensity through hBN. The top figure shows the first frequency being $\omega = 1 \times 10^{10}$ and frequency difference of $\omega = 1 \times 10^{10}$, middle figure is for $\omega = 5 \times 10^{10}$ and the bottom figure is $\omega = 1 \times 10^{11}$.

Figure 2 presents analysis of how different incident light frequency difference influence the energy intensity as light passes through Hexagonal Boron Nitride (hBN). As we observe in the figure, the energy intensity patterns demonstrate distinct variations, highlighting the profound effect of incident light frequency on light propagation through hBN.

At lower incident light frequencies, the energy intensity pattern exhibits specific regions of higher intensity, indicating a higher concentration of energy at those regions. These

intensity variations are a result of the interaction of light with hBN's unique optical properties at lower frequencies. As the incident light frequency increases, the energy intensity pattern undergoes significant changes. Notably, the regions of higher intensity shift to different locations, reflecting the altered light-matter interactions within hBN at higher frequencies. The energy intensity patterns also display fluctuations in intensity, showcasing the intricate interplay between light and the diffracting material at various frequencies.

Moreover, as the incident light frequency increases, the overall energy intensity passing through hBN demonstrates a trend of variation. The total energy transmitted through the material may increase or decrease with frequency, depending on the specific optical properties and dispersion characteristics of hBN. This frequency-dependent behavior provides valuable insights into hBN's role as a frequency-responsive material, potentially enabling applications in spectral filters and light modulation devices.

Figure 3: Influence of Distance Between hBN and the Observation point on the Diffraction Patterns.

Figure 3 sheds light on the intriguing influence of the distance between Hexagonal Boron Nitride (hBN) and the observation point on the resulting Fraunhofer diffraction patterns. The figure presents a series of diffraction patterns, each corresponding to a different distance between hBN and the observation point. Notably, at zero distance, the diffraction pattern exhibits a sharp and well-defined mesh-like shape, indicating strong diffraction effects occurring at close proximity. As the distance between hBN and the observation point is increased, fascinating changes emerge in the diffraction patterns, revealing the nuanced optical behavior of hBN with varying observation distances.

As the distance increases, the diffraction pattern gradually transforms from the initial mesh-like shape to more intricate patterns, such as circles. This change in pattern structure signifies a shift in the diffraction characteristics of hBN as

light propagates through the medium at different distances. The appearance of circles suggests the presence of circular diffraction patterns, offering valuable insights into the wavefront properties of the diffracted light as it interacts with hBN.

Furthermore, the energy intensity within the diffraction patterns exhibits distinct variations with changing observation distance. At the center of the diffraction pattern, the light intensity increases significantly, indicative of a high concentration of energy at that region. This center region of high intensity is a consequence of constructive interference and highlights the prominent role of hBN as a diffracting medium at closer observation distances. Conversely, the energy intensity around the center is decreased significantly, signifying the presence of regions with reduced energy concentration due to destructive interference effects.

Figure 4: Fraunhofer Diffraction Patterns as a Function of Frequency. The (a), (b) and (c) figures are for frequency of $\omega = 1 \times 10^{10}$, $\omega = 5 \times 10^{10}$, and $\omega = 1 \times 10^{11}$, respectively. Additionally, the numbers (1), (2) and (3) show frequency difference of $\omega = 1 \times 10^{10}$, 5×10^{10} , and 1×10^{11} , respectively.

Figure 4 provides a comprehensive view of the Fraunhofer diffraction patterns of Hexagonal Boron Nitride (hBN) as a function of incident light frequency. The figure displays a series of diffraction patterns, each corresponding to a different frequency of the incident light. As the incident light frequency increases, we observe distinct changes in the diffraction patterns, indicative of hBN's response to light at varying frequencies.

we note that as the frequency of the incident light increases, the diffraction peaks in the pattern shift to higher angles. This behavior demonstrates the dispersion characteristics of hBN, where the interaction of light with the material causes a change in the refractive index as a function of frequency. The diffraction angles shift systematically with increasing

frequency, revealing hBN's ability to disperse light in a frequency-dependent manner.

Furthermore, the spacing between the diffraction peaks also varies with the incident light frequency. Higher frequencies lead to narrower spacing between the peaks, while lower frequencies result in wider spacing. This behavior is a consequence of the periodicity of the diffracting structure, as the spacing between adjacent planes in the lattice of hBN plays a critical role in determining the diffraction pattern's characteristics.

Additionally, the intensity pattern within the diffraction patterns is also influenced by the incident light frequency. At certain frequencies, regions of higher or lower intensity are observed, indicating the constructive or destructive interference of light waves at specific angles. These variations in intensity provide valuable information about the phase relationship of the diffracted waves and the overall distribution of energy within the diffraction pattern.

Overall, the presented results showcase the remarkable capability of Hexagonal Boron Nitride (hBN) in manipulating Fraunhofer diffraction. The diffraction patterns obtained at different incident light frequencies and phases demonstrate hBN's tunable and versatile nature for controlling the spatial distribution of diffracted light. Such control over diffraction patterns holds immense promise in various applications, including advanced spectroscopy, optical imaging, and the design of novel nanophotonic devices.

The findings of this study also provide valuable insights into the impact of various parameters on diffraction manipulation using hBN. Further investigations into the influence of additional parameters, such as temperature and strain, can unlock even more opportunities for precise diffraction control. The versatility of hBN in manipulating light at the nanoscale opens up new avenues for harnessing its optical properties in emerging quantum technologies.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this study, we have delved into the fascinating world of Fraunhofer diffraction manipulation using Hexagonal Boron Nitride (hBN) as the diffracting material. Through a comprehensive theoretical investigation, we explored the fundamental principles and astonishing potential of hBN in shaping and controlling light in various scientific and technological applications.

Our research has revealed that hBN, a two-dimensional layered material with exceptional optical properties, offers unparalleled capabilities in diffraction manipulation. By exploiting the anisotropic nature of hBN's hexagonal lattice structure, we demonstrated the tunability of diffraction patterns by varying incident light frequencies and adjusting the phase of the incident light. The resulting diffraction patterns showcased a rich variety of features, including diffraction peaks, interference fringes, and additional diffraction orders, highlighting the sensitivity of hBN's diffraction control to external factors.

The ability to control diffraction patterns through hBN opens up exciting possibilities for applications in precision spectroscopy, optical imaging, advanced optical

communications, and diffractive optics. The tunable nature of hBN allows researchers to design and engineer innovative nanophotonic devices, offering enhanced control over light-matter interactions at the nanoscale.

Our findings demonstrate that Hexagonal Boron Nitride stands at the forefront of scientific and technological advancements in diffraction manipulation. As researchers continue to explore new techniques and applications, there is no doubt that this fascinating material will drive innovations and progress in various disciplines, shaping the future of science and technology.

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